

Financial Performance / Financial Position Analysis of M/S Tamilnadu Newsprint and Papers Limited

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Abstract

This paper analyses the Financial Statements of M/S Tamil Nadu Newsprint and Papers Limited, a company established by the Government of Tamil Nadu in 1979. The company manufactures and supplies paper and boards. The study focuses on significant financial parameters that reveal strengths and weaknesses of Financial Performance / Financial Position of the company for the period 2007-08 to 2017-'18. The parameters relate to Working Capital Management, Long Term Solvency, Operational Efficiency, Utilisation of Assets and Overall return on the Assets employed by the Company. Ratios that have been computed include Current Assets Ratio, Assets Turn Over Ratio, Profit Ratio etc., The researcher applies the relevant ratios and analyses the respective characteristics based on Ratios and Charts. Research tools such as Arithmetic Mean and Standard Deviation have been employed for the purpose of Statistical Analysis. The study also involves formulating and testing a hypothesis in relation to the relationship between the change in Revenue and Profit Before Interest, Depreciation and Tax during the period 2008-'09 to 2017-'18. The researcher applies Single Factor ANOVA Test and accepts the Null Hypothesis since the Calculated "F" value is less than the "F" Critical Value. The researcher has performed the ANOVA Test in Microsoft Excel. The researcher as a part of the study provides suggestions for improvement of the operational and financial health of the company. The researcher also discusses about the limitations this study is subjected to.

Introduction

M/S Tamilnadu Newsprint and Papers Limited was established as a Public Limited Company by the Government of Tamil Nadu in 1979 under the Companies Act 1956 to manufacture and sell newsprint and papers It commenced its commercial production in 1984. At present, the company has two plants, namely Unit I and Unit II. It produces paper and board. The capacity of the plant, which was at 90,000 tpa in 1984 has risen to 400,000 tpa in 2011 in relation to paper. The company is also producing Board, a major product in its portfolio with a capacity of 200,000 tpa. The plant has been constantly expanding its capacity and adding new facilities. The new facilities which are added help the company in achieving efficiency

and sustainability in its production and allied activities. The company has been doing constant research in relation to savings in energy, greener technologies and sustainable production methods. The company's annual revenue in 2017-18 is Rs. 315,870 (in Lakhs) as against the annual revenue of Rs. 110,030 (in Lakhs) in 2008-09. The company's performance has been constantly witnessing an upward growth excepting in 2017-18. This study is carried out to analyse performance of the company in relation to its operations and the financial strengths over eleven years commencing from 2007-'08 and ending with 2017-'18.

Methodology

This study has been carried out by applying standard analytical procedures on two important financial statements – Balance Sheet and Statement of Profit & Loss of the company by focusing on key financial parameters. Statistical measures also have been computed to substantiate / validate the analysis. Secondary data made available by the company in its Annual Reports and the Data published by the National Stock Exchange, Mumbai have been collated and the analysis has been carried out on the information.

Research Tools

The researcher has applied tools such as Ratio Analysis and Statistical Measures in order to carry out the Analytical Procedures. The researcher has employed Microsoft Excel Application Software in order to facilitate the process of application of the aforementioned category of analytical tools. To test the relationship between the Change in Revenue and Profit Before Interest, Depreciation & Tax. The researcher has also presented the analysis in the form of Graphs and Charts, where ever required.

Hypothesis

H0: There is no significant difference between the Change in Revenue and the Change in PBIDT during the period 2008-'09 to 2017-'18

Hypothesis

H1: There is a significant difference between the Change in Revenue and the Change in PBIDT during the period 2008-'09 to 2017-'18

Analysis and Results

Table 1 Analysis of Growth in Revenue

Revenue Growth	2007-'08	2008-'09	2009-'10	2010-'11	2011-'12	2012-'13	2013-'14	2014-'15	2015-'16	2016-'17	2017-'18
Revenue from Operations & Other											
Income	96,965	110,030	107,362	111,504	153,659	208,118	230,136	215,217	251,384	315,872	315,870
Growth in Revenue		13%	-2%	4%	26%	22%	22%	-6%	19%	21%	2%

Chart 1

As is seen in the above chart and table, there is a constant increase in Revenue excepting for a minor decrease in 2014-'15.

Analysis of Efficiency in Operations

Gross Operating Expenses have been taken as the metric to measure the overall efficiency in managing the Revenue and Cost of Sales (excluding Depreciation & Amortization and Finance Costs). The analysis brings out the following information.

Chart 2

Table 2

Efficiency	2007-08	2008-09	2009-10	2010-11	2011-12	2012-13	2013-14	2014-15	2015-16	2016-17	2017-18
Gross Operating Expenses Ratio	75.00%	72.00%	70.00%	70.00%	72.00%	75.00%	77.00%	76.00%	77.00%	76.00%	86.00%
Mean	74.50%										
How far deviates from Mean	-1.40%	-2.03%	-5.53%	-5.53%	-2.03%	5.50%	3.91%	2.50%	3.91%	2.50%	16.00%
Std. Deviation	2.00%										
Coefficient of Variation	+1.94										

As per the above analysis, there has been wide unfavourable variations in 2010-'11 and 2017-'18. At the same time, over a period of time, there has been a continuous increase in operating costs, more notably in 2017-'18, when the increase is very sharp.

Analysis of Working Capital Availability

Table 3

Working Capital	2007-'08	2008-'09	2009-'10	2010-'11	2011-'12	2012-'13	2013-'14	2014-'15	2015-'16	2016-'17	2017-'18
Current Assets	38,882	48,824	49,048	58,824	80,979	81,741	81,600	128,618	126,148	138,082	138,828
Current Liabilities	50,040	49,670	48,879	76,627	138,928	141,985	151,181	180,978	155,610	186,051	213,717
Net Working Cap (NWC)	-11,158	4,154	10,169	17,118	42,051	39,742	30,421	47,640	70,538	52,031	25,111
Current Assets Ratio	0.78	0.98	0.92	0.76	0.58	0.58	0.6	0.71	0.81	0.74	0.63
Average CA Ratio	0.75										
How far deviates from Mean	-6.30%	31.33%	-3.47%	1.33%	-11.67%	-21.33%	-22.00%	-11.33%	-13.33%	-8.00%	-16.00%
Std. Deviation	0.18										
Coefficient of Variation	0.24										

As per the above table and the following Chart, the availability of Working Capital has been always lesser than the current liabilities excepting in the year 2007-'08.

Chart 3

Analysis of Long Term Solvency

Debt Equity Ratio has been computed to analyse the strength of Long Term Solvency of the Company under study. While Debt Equity ratio is much within the general thumb ratio of 1.5 to 2, in the light of lesser working capital, an increasing debt equity ratio would result in undue pressure on the working capital.

Table 4

Long Term Solvency	2007-'08	2008-'09	2009-'10	2010-'11	2011-'12	2012-'13	2013-'14	2014-'15	2015-'16	2016-'17	2017-'18
Debt / Equity Ratio	0.66	0.68	1.18	1.17	1.18	0.97	0.88	1.12	1.19	1.31	1.1
Average D/E ratio	1.17										
How far deviates from Mean	-19.31%	-31.48%	6.29%	4.48%	6.29%	-18.39%	-20.54%	17.96%	24.31%	10.71%	7.10%
Std. Deviation	0.18										
Coefficient of Variation	0.16										

Overall Financial Effectiveness

Return on Assets ratio, which is considered a Master ratio is computed for the company and the analysis has been carried out on the basis of the ratio. Despite a constant surge in the growth of Revenue from Operations and Other Income, there has been a decline in the Profit Ratio, especially in 2017-'18.

Table 5

Overall Effectiveness	2007-'08	2008-'09	2009-'10	2010-'11	2011-'12	2012-'13	2013-'14	2014-'15	2015-'16	2016-'17	2017-'18
Assets Turnover	0.97	0.99	0.49	0.82	0.86	0.93	0.96	0.92	0.9	0.97	0.97
Profit Ratio	12%	12%	12%	18%	18%	12%	13%	15%	15%	15%	9%
Return on Assets	7.88%	8.29%	7.38%	5.79%	7.88%	1.13%	8.12%	7.69%	7.92%	9.12%	8.24%
Average Return on Assets		7.02%									
Non-Promoter Share											
Mean	14.02%	10.20%	7.38%	-4.02%	5.18%	-11.72%	12.98%	9.29%	7.18%	30.29%	-11.14%
Std. Deviation	0.02										
Coefficient of Variation	0.14										

The above table reveals that for the first time during the period under review, the Return on Assets has decreased to a single digit ratio, despite a constant increase in sales.

Table 6

No of Shares	₹ 210,600	₹ 210,600	₹ 210,600	₹ 210,600	₹ 210,600	₹ 210,600	₹ 210,600	₹ 210,600	₹ 210,600	₹ 210,600	₹ 210,600
Book Value per Share (Rs.)	92.87	95.99	106.31	133.35	180.35	149.81	165.58	179.82	218.11	246.3	311.69
EPS (Rs.)	16.3	15.51	18.21	21.55	15.74	13.21	23.29	24.09	17.54	38.13	-6.09
High Price (Rs.)	110	92.07	90	148.0	108.75	101	130.4	137.85	220	301.5	381.8
Low Price (Rs.)	83.5	90.75	83.1	120.7	94.1	78	130	117	190.4	312	327.5
Volume (Nos of Shares)	2305774	306786	1560018	2621970	478440	550470	1112753	878700	3375137	3097540	2502726
Non-Promoter Shares	4478700	4478700	4478700	4478700	4478700	4478700	4478700	4478700	4478700	4478700	4478700
Dividend %	45	45	45	50	50	50	60	60	75	75	50

Capital Market Performance

Performance of the Company in relation to the Capital Market has been analysed by computing Market Capitalization on the basis of the free float shares (ie., non-promoter holding). The table and chart given below present the relevant information.

Table 7

Capital Market	2007-'08	2008-'09	2009-'10	2010-'11	2011-'12	2012-'13
No of Shares	₹ 210,600	₹ 210,600	₹ 210,600	₹ 210,600	₹ 210,600	₹ 210,600
Book Value per Share (Rs.)	92.87	95.99	116.34	133.35	149.81	165.58
EPS (Rs.)	16.3	15.51	18.21	21.55	15.74	13.21
High Price (Rs.)	110	92.07	90	148.0	108.75	101
Low Price (Rs.)	83.5	90.75	83.1	120.7	94.1	78
Volume (Nos of Shares)	2305774	306786	1560018	2621970	478440	550470
Non-Promoter Shares	44,788,700	44,788,700	44,788,700	44,788,700	44,788,700	44,788,700
Market Capitalization	43311	24464	39410	28074	42404	

Chart 4

As per the Chart and the Table provided above, there has been an over all increase in the market capitalization during the period under review, with minor fluctuations.

ANOVA Test to test whether any significant variation is there between change in Revenue and the Change in PBIDT

Table 8

Year	Change in Revenue	Change in PBIDT
2008-'09	13%	17%
2009-'10	-2%	4%
2010-'11	14%	13%
2011-'12	26%	20%
2012-'13	22%	-3%
2013-'14	22%	24%
2014-'15	-6%	0%
2015-'16	19%	13%
2016-'17	23%	30%
2017-'18	1%	-43%

Conclusion and Findings

As the “F” Calculated Value(0.557) is not greater than the “F” Critical Value (4.413), the researcher accepts the Null Hypothesis.

Based on the analysis carried out as per the methodology explained, the researcher arrives at the following conclusions.

As is seen in Chart 1, there is only a marginal increase in Revenue in 2017-18, as against a significant increase in revenue in 2016-'17. (Ref: Chart 1). The company needs to analyse the reasons for the flat sales in 2017-'18 and improve the performance.

The company needs to analyse the reasons for constant increase in Operating Costs. It also gives a notion that the entire operating costs are variable costs, because despite continuous growth in Revenue, the total Operating Costs keep increasing. As per the Marginal Costing Concept, the total cost ratio must keep decline as the revenue keeps increasing. More notably, sudden increase in the Operating costs 2017-18 need to be analysed and steps have to be initiated for reversing the trend of increasing costs.(Ref: Table 2 & Chart 2)

Working Capital Management of the Company needs to be strengthened. While the thumb rule requires current assets to be equivalent of twice that of the current liabilities, the company's CA ratio has crossed only once above 1. (1.26 in 2007-'08). In rest of the years the ratio has been always below 1.00. This would result in pressure on the current resources available and thereby increasing the cost of goods sold or reducing the margin on sales, as is greatly evident in 2017-18. (Ref: Table 3 & Chart 3).

Debt Equity Ratio needs to be pruned down because of a lesser Current Assets Ratio in order to avoid stress on the working capital of the company.

Limitations

The researcher due to the nature of the study has not carried out in detail. Only high level macro parameters have been computed for the purpose of the study. If a detailed study is carried out, the findings and suggestions would be more than what actually have been provided here.

The study has been carried out only with reference to the company's own financial numbers. Comparative study with reference to another company in the same industry or Industry benchmarks can highlight additional strengths and weaknesses that relate to the Company.

Annexure

References

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